

The Effect of Auditor Behavior on Audit Judgments in Public Accountant Firms in the City of Jakarta, Indonesia

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Abstract

This study aims to find empirical evidence and analyze the significant influence on the behavior of auditors who are proxied in audit experience, compliance pressure and independence of Audit Judgment. The sample used in this study were senior auditors, partners and managers working in public accounting firms in the city of Jakarta, Indonesia, which were recorded in the Public Accounting Firm Directory published by the Indonesian Institute of Certified Public Accountants (IAPI) in 2019. Sampling was done randomly and obtained as many as 90 respondents. The analysis technique used in this study is the Smart PLS program with a significant level of 5%.

The results showed that audit experience and independence had a significant effect on Audit Judgments, while compliance pressure did not have a significant effect on Audit Judgments.

Keywords: *audit experience, compliance pressure, independence and Audit Judgment*

BACKGROUND

Financial statements that have been audited by a public accountant are expected to be free from mistakes such as material misstatement and can be trusted with the truth of the report so that it can be used as a reference. Regulations on Public Accountants in Indonesia are regulated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 5 of 2011 which is more specifically described in Government of Republic of Indonesia Regulation Number 20 of 2015 related to Public Accountant Practices, Regulation of the Minister of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia Number 154, PMK 01 of 2017 regarding Development and Supervision of Public Accountants and Financial Services Authority Regulation Number 13 / POJK.03 / 2017 regarding the Use of Public Accountant Services and Public Accountant Offices in Financial Services Activities.

With the increasing need for audits on these financial statements, the services of an independent auditor are needed. An independent auditor will convey certainty over the results of audits of financial statements that are free from misstatements, can be relied upon and trusted as the basis for making business decisions (Sofiani & Tjondro, 2019).

The task of the auditor is to audit the financial statements of an entity and provide opinions and thoughts related to the reasonableness of the financial statements. In addition, it also reviews whether the entity has consistently applied accounting standard policies that are in accordance with Indonesian standards. So that auditors who are trusted should have sufficient competence in maintaining trust with clients and users of financial statements.

The auditor profession cannot be separated from a problem. Sometimes the auditor does a job not in line with the auditor's professional standards, but in accordance with the wishes of the leadership or client that causes the auditor to benefit the client and is very limited in doing the audit work due to pressure from the boss or client.

Examples of cases that occur are the case of PT. Sunprima Nusantara Financing (SNP Finance) and Deloitte Indonesia in September 2018. PT. SNP Finance is a business that offers credit or installment payments for household purchases. Sources of funds obtained by PT. The SNP Finance comes from banks or debt securities. One of the biggest funding sources of PT. SNP Finance comes from the capital of PT. Bank Mandiri (Persero) TBK. But over time, PT. SNP Finance is experiencing bad credit, so that it impacts other banks that have lent capital to PT. SNP Finance. One of the steps taken by PT. SNP Finance in overcoming the bad credit is by raising bonds in the form of Medium Term Notes (MTN) which are ranked by Pefindo, rating agencies and have been based on financial reports that have been audited by Deloitte's Public Accountant Office. But when the emergence of the MTN, PT. SNP Finance does not involve the Financial Services Authority (OJK) in carrying out the MTN issuance process. OJK prohibits the issuance of MTN without OJK's permission and must prepare to coordinate with the ministry of finance related to the work of public accounting firms. Even though it is confidential, it should still need ranking because it can be bought

and sold. At that time, the FSA immediately imposed sanctions by stopping all business activities of PT. SNP Finance. Within 6 (six) months PT. SNP Finance is required to take corrective action, if it does not carry out its business license will be revoked.

In this case the Financial Services Authority (OJK) has communicated and coordinated with the Financial Professional Development Center (PPPK). PPPK seeks the essence of the problem. From the results of the examination carried out, then the PPPK can conclude about the indication of serious violations of the accounting profession standards when auditing the 2012 to 2016 financial statements that have already been audited. PPPK noted the unavailability of reasonableness in the assertion of occurrence and the assertion of separate account income and financing limits. Public accountant who has audited PT. SNP Finance namely, Public Accountants Marlinna, Merliyana, and Syamsul (MMS) apparently have not implemented policies that are sufficiently related to fraud risk detection methods and responses to fraud risk. The Ministry of Finance has also imposed sanctions on Deloitte Indonesia by providing advice in the form of formulating policies and procedures on methods for handling the quality of public accountants related to the threat of closeness to subordinates in the senior engagement team. (Cnnindonesia.com/kronologi-snp-finance)

The failed audit case has the effect of lawsuits, the fall of professionalism, and the loss of public trust. Also in maintaining the good name of the auditor over public accountants. The most important thing to protect the reputation of an auditor is to carry out preventive measures in the event of an audit failure. And generate public suspicion about the experience of auditors who are considered less mastering as the accountant profession and open up new suspicions related to how the experience of the external auditor's work ability so far to determine assessments and views (Putra & Rani, 2016). Therefore, the experience and expertise of auditors need to be continually added, because business growth is now faster and the availability of various changes that apply to these standards and codes of ethics.

Audit experience is one of the factors of auditor behavior that can affect Audit Judgment. The auditor's experience is expected to have a very significant impact on the auditor's work evaluation. Auditors who have less experience have more opportunities to make big mistakes than auditors who have experience (Putra & rani, 2016). The auditor's experience can be seen based on the length of time the auditor has worked as an auditor. The auditor's experience can also be ascertained based on how large the number of companies that have been audited and how large the number of audit tasks that have been done. The auditor's flying hours will affect how the auditor responds to the results of the audit he has done.

The second factor that influences auditor behavior on Audit Judgments is compliance pressure. Compliance pressure is an event that makes an auditor bear the pressure when going to carry out his audit activities to deal with the instructions of the leadership or client (the entity observed) to carry out what they want even though sometimes his actions are outside the limits of auditor professionalism standards (Pangesti et., Al 2018). Obedience pressure tends to originate from the leadership or based on junior to senior auditors as well as demands originating from an entity that has been observed to work on deviations from the standards that have been determined (Ariyantini, 2014). In their audit work, an auditor sometimes has pressure in the compliance process. This can be seen from the amount of pressure exerted by superiors, the entity (auditee), or fellow colleagues so that the auditor behaves and behaves in deviation from the existing professional standards.

The third factor auditor's behavior which also has an impact on Audit Judgment is Independence. Independence is behavior that is free from other influences, meaning that the attitude of independence cannot be controlled and cannot be bound to other parties, must be intellectual and be neutral (not in favor of anyone) to weigh the facts that occur in giving their opinions (Drupadi & Sudana, 2015). The higher the auditor's independence attitude makes the Judgment issued more carefully.

Based on the background above, this study aims to find empirical evidence and analyze the significant influence of auditor's behavior to be proxeed on audit experience, compliance pressure and independence of Audit Judgment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Attribution Theory

This research is supported by attribution theory proposed by Fritz Heider, a theory that describes the attitude of a person to be able to know how the process of determining the triggers and reasons for one's

attitude. The relationship between attribution theory and the variables in this study are audit experience, obedience pressure and independence. Audit experience looks more into behavior highly experienced auditors will maintain behavior or ethics while working. Strict pressure is more on when the auditor is carrying out the task, usually the compliance pressure experienced by the auditor appears two sides, namely superiors and auditees which will later lead to a dilemma in applying the standards of the public accountant profession. Independence means behavior that is free from other influences, therefore an auditor cannot be controlled and is not bound to any party in decision making. The higher the level of independence of an auditor, the more accurate the resulting Judgment.

Audit Judgment

Judgment is interpreted as an opinion, decision and consideration. The quality of work performed by an auditor can be obtained based on the results of Judgment quality and the conditions chosen. Decisions or considerations made by auditors must have an influence, decisions taken can obtain results with effective quality and vice versa (R. Komalasari & Hernawati, 2015). Audit judgment is an individual judgment or auditor's point of view to understand data that has an impact on the results of the documentation of the evidence and the determination of the opinion carried out by the auditor of an entity's financial statements (Farma, 2016)

In several previous studies (Sumanto & Rosdiana, 2019), (Pangesti et al., 2018) and (Nyoman & Tibe, 2019) using the determination of the level of Matter, transaction engineering, auditor ability, internal handling methods, audit procedures and audit risks used as an indicator of measurement of Audit Judgment, in this study the determination of the level of matrix, transaction engineering, auditor ability, internal handling methods of audit procedures and audit risk will be used as indicators to measure Audit Judgments.

Audit auditor's judgment is needed because an audit cannot be carried out on all the evidence because it takes a long time and the budget is not small, which also makes the audit process ineffective. This evidence is used to express an opinion on the financial statements. Audit judgment requires four levels of audit procedures for financial statements, are:

1. Acceptance of the engagement as an agreement between the two parties between the auditor and a company that is represented by management. The client or management provides audit evidence of the financial statements to the auditor and the auditor must meet the financial statements in accordance with his field or competence. When the auditor receives an audit engagement, the first step undertaken in auditing the financial statements is the auditor decides whether to accept the audit work or refuse the audit work. In carrying out Audit Judgments on various events, namely management integrity, independence, objectivity, the capability of the auditor in using his competent expertise carefully and in conclusion the determination is made between the two choices, which is to accept or not an audit agreement.
2. Planning the audit process, at this stage requires several activities that must be fulfilled, namely by knowing the client's industry and understanding the business being carried out, carrying out analytical procedures, ensuring materiality, applying audit risk and inherent risk and knowing the structure of internal control and determining control risk. An auditor must be able to identify the consequences and materiality rating of the account balance that has been determined. Judgment at this stage is used to determine the audit policies that are subsequently carried out because Judgment at the initial stage of the audit is determined according to the assessment of the materiality rating predicted.
3. Implementation of audit testing, where in this stage the auditor will do analytic, control and substantive testing. Analytical testing is done by the auditor by understanding and studying the data and information provided by the client and then comparing it with other data and information. Then testing more controls to check and verify the effectiveness of the client's internal controls. And substantive testing is a test that is intended to find out the mistakes in the financial statements. If related to the financial statements, the judgment made by the auditor will have an influence on the opinion of the auditor regarding the reasonableness of the financial statements. Factors that shape an auditor's opinion related to the reasonableness of the client's financial statements, namely the ability of the client's internal handling methods, regular accounting transactions using generally accepted accounting principles, whether there are audit barriers carried out from the client and the suitability of accounting transaction data collection. So that it can be reported about Judgment that is the main activity for conducting audit activities.

4. Audit Reporting, where the results of the audit report are audit work that has been completed. Audit reports cannot be made carelessly, but in a good audit report must include the type or service that has been provided, then the object that has been audited, the scope of the audit, audit objectives and results of the audit and provide suggestions if there are errors or deficiencies towards the report. Judgment decisions issued by auditors to end their audit activities make a significant impact on the final opinion produced. Then by indirect means will also influence whether or not the correctness of the provisions drawn from outside the company and entrust the audit financial statements to be his reference.

In terms of the auditor's personal attitude can be assessed that really has an influence in the implementation of the Judgment Audit and is a concern for accounting, research and academic practitioners. Therefore the increase in interest is not made balanced with the growth and development of research, especially in the accounting discipline of attitudes which in various studies but the condition was ultimately not made an important point.

According to Jamilah (2007) in Hasnidar et al., (2018) argues that the Audit Judgment decided by the auditor based on its level is divided into three, namely:

1. The auditor's judgment regarding the materiality stage. The materiality and audit risk are taken into account by the auditor when creating the agenda and implementation of financial statement audits and are influenced by the auditor's opinion of the needs of someone who has sufficient knowledge. Thus, materiality has a relationship with judgment (judgment) and when associated with risk assessment, the assessment can affect the rules for achieving audit targets.
2. Auditor's judgment related to the audit risk stage. When making an audit plan, the auditor must use his judgment to determine the stage of a small audit risk as well as the first assessment of the materiality stage using a method that desires, for limited circumstances in the audit process, the auditor can present audit evidence that is valuable in order to gain compliant trust regarding financial statements. it is independent of material misstatement. The auditor's judgment regarding audit risk and materiality relating to other conditions is needed to determine the nature, timing and scope of the audit procedure and when assessing the results of the procedure. And when taking Judgment, the auditor must examine the audit risk problem in addition to the concept of materiality.
3. Auditors' judgment regarding going concern. An auditor is not only required to know the conditions that are only found in the financial statements but also needs to suspect a potential that can affect the survival of a company. The auditor observes all aspects related to the entity when it wants to withdraw the provisions related to going concern. This sharp assessment is very useful in order to give the auditor the opportunity to produce and give a careful evaluation of the client's understanding in maintaining its operations. If the auditor has conclusions regarding in doubt about the continuity of an entity's development, it requires the auditor to take into account its impact on the financial statements and whether the method of expressing going concern has met.

Audit Experience

The auditor's experience as one of the auditor's behaviors is an aspect that can influence Audit Judgment. The auditor's experience is calculated to have a very significant impact on the auditor's work evaluation. Auditors who lack experience will have more opportunities to make big mistakes than auditors who have experience (Putra & rani, 2016). The auditor's experience can be seen based on the length of time the auditor has worked as an auditor. The auditor's experience can also be ascertained based on how large the company has been audited and how much inspection work has been done. A person's experience arises because of mistakes in the past which eventually become a learning so that later it will add insight into carrying out his duties as an auditor and become even better in the future.

In several previous studies (Priyoga & Ayem, 2019) and (Sumanto & Rosdiana, 2019) using the length of work, the large number of audit assignments and the audited company classification were used as indicators of measuring auditor experience. So in this study the length of work, the large number of audit assignments and the type of company being audited will be used as an indicator to measure audit experience.

Compliance Pressure

Compliance pressure, which is also one of the auditors' behaviors, is a pressure that comes based on the personal because they receive an instruction on another person, even if it is from the leader or client.

This situation certainly raises pressure on the auditor's personal to continue to follow orders or not follow the orders of the client or the leadership. Therefore, an auditor is often met with a difficult and confusing situation in applying the auditor's profession standards for withdrawing his provisions (Tampubolon, 2018).

Nadya & Maria (2019) revealed that when an auditor cannot obey the orders of his clients or superiors to deviate from professional standards at the risk of the auditor accepting problems with the client or his supervisor, the auditor's objectivity is higher and the auditor can express client misstatements in the auditor's report give effect to the correct Auditor Judgment.

Auditors are often faced with provisions whose results are not enough just by the code of ethics or based on applicable accounting standards. The first assessment of a decision is ethics, although there are often different types of conflicting needs. Obtained two conflicting needs, namely real conflict and latent conflict. Real conflict is a conflict that has an impact on Judgment problems that are available, whereas latent conflict is a conflict that can affect judgment in the future. For example, further conflict can take place to the auditor whose income is more dominant over one of the relatively large clients. Even though the situation was not troublesome at the time, but when it could take place it required a negative adaptation to profit. Clients in this situation may not accept the adaptation by giving a warning that they will switch to other auditors (Sofiani & Tjondro, 2019)

In several previous studies, namely (Priyoga & Ayem, 2019), (Sumanto & Rosdiana, 2019) and (Tampubolon, 2018) using obedience pressure through leadership, obedience pressure through clients, compliance of auditors to professionals and adherence to ethical codes and standards used as an indicator of obedience pressure measurement. So in this study the obedience pressure from superiors, obedience pressure from the client, obedience of auditors to professionals and pressure to the code of ethics and standards will be used as an indicator to measure compliance pressure.

Independence

One more thing that is also an auditor's behavior that is considered important is independence, which is behavior that is free from other impacts, meaning that the attitude of independence cannot be controlled and cannot rely on other parts, must be intellectual and must take an honest, and objective attitude (not in favor of anyone) to take into account the facts that occur and provide opinions (Drupadi & Sudana, 2015). The higher the independence stage of an auditor, it is expected that the Judgment results issued will be more thorough.

Independence also means that there is honesty in the auditor's person to calculate an existing truth and an objective calculation, not in favor of the auditor's person in order to formulate and express his opinion (R. Komalasari & Hernawati, 2015).

In several previous studies (Priyoga & Ayem, 2019) and (Nadya & Maria, 2019) using free from the influence of other parties, receiving audit fees, relationship with clients, only subject to the correct and free according to the law as an indicator of independence measurement, then in this study free from the influence of other parties, the receipt of fees for audit services, relations with clients, only subject to the right and free according to the law will be used as an indicator to measure independence.

Effect of Auditor Behavior, namely Audit Experience on Audit Judgment

Audit experience is an experience that an auditor has to carry out control and based on the number of tasks received, but the process is different and the length of time the auditor takes on his profession can improve his understanding of error detection. If the auditor's experience increases, then Audit Judgment will face an increase. The large number of auditors' experience on the audit aspect can make it easier for auditors to work on obligations to completion which lead to having a similar system (Priyoga & Ayem, 2019).

In research conducted by Priyoga & Ayem (2019), Ariyantini (2014), Murtadha (2018), Ardiani et al., (2019), Nyoman & Tibe (2019), Sofiani & Tjondro (2019) who suggested that audit experience influences significant to Audit Judgment which means that high audit experience will improve skills so that the ability to think or act will be better too.

To test the effect of audit experience on Audit Judgments, the researcher suspects that an auditor who has high experience will be easier to make decisions than an auditor who still has no experience. So the hypothesis put forward namely:

H₁: Auditor's experience has a significant influence on Audit Judgments.

Effect of Audit Behavior, namely Compliance Pressure on Audit Judgment

Compliance Pressure is pressure that comes from within a person because he accepts an assignment from another person, as well as the leader or client of the entity. The situation certainly raises pressure on the auditors themselves to continue to follow orders or do not follow the orders of leaders and clients. Therefore, an auditor is often met with a difficult situation in applying the auditor's profession standards for withdrawing his provisions (Tampubolon, 2018). According to Nadya & Maria (2019) When an auditor cannot obey a client or supervisor's orders to deviate from professional standards at the risk of the auditor accepting problems with the client or his supervisor, the auditor's objectivity is higher and the auditor can express client misstatements in the auditor's report that provides the impact on the correct Auditor Judgment.

In a study conducted by Tampubolon (2018) and Agustini & Merkusiwati (2016) which stated that the pressure of obedience has a significant influence on Audit Judgment, which means that it relates to an auditor in any situation and condition because there are duties from the leadership and pressure from the client to follow the behavior deviating from professional standards, junior auditors do not have the courage to not follow the task and would rather follow the order.

To test the effect of Compliance Pressure on Audit Judgments, the researcher suspects that an auditor does not want to take the risk of losing his job and doing orders even if the behavior deviates from professional standards. So the hypothesis put forward namely:

H₂: Compliance Pressure has a significant effect on Audit Judgment.

Effect of Audit Behavior, namely Independence of Audit Judgment

Independence is behavior that is free from other impacts, which means that the attitude of independence cannot be controlled and cannot rely on other groups, must be intellectual and must be credible and neutral (not in favor of anyone) in assessing information that occurs and gives the holder (Drupadi & Sudana , 2015). The higher the independence stage of an auditor, making the Judgment issued more thorough.

In a study conducted by Ramdani & Hendy (2019), Nadya & Maria (2019) and R. Komalasari & Hernawati (2015) suggested that independence had a significant effect on Audit Judgment.

To test the effect of Independence on Audit Judgment, the researcher suspects that related auditors who have great independence cannot be controlled from any group and reject requests if there is a desire from another party to commit irregularities. So the hypothesis put forward namely:

H₃: Independence has a significant influence on Audit Judgment.

Phenomenon

PT Sunprima Nusantara Financing (SNP Finance) and Deloitte Indonesia are cases of audit failure that have the effect of which are lawsuits, loss of professionalism, and lack of public confidence. And the loss of the good name of an auditor from a public accountant

Figure 1. Framework

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The design of this study uses a quantitative approach to determine whether there is an influence or not between the hypothesized variables. The type of data used is primary data and the sampling technique used is probability sampling using the simple random sampling method. Sampling used in this study by distributing questionnaires which are a collection of written questions and have been formulated in advance so that respondents can directly fill in the questionnaire and are descriptive or explanatory (Uma Sekaran and Roger Bougie, 2017 p.170).

The population in this study are auditors who have senior positions, partners and managers (can be seen in appendix 1) who work in the Public Accountant Office in the City of Jakarta, Indonesia and are registered in the IAPI 2019 Directory and are randomly drawn. The sample in this study amounted to 90 respondents from 18 selected public accounting firms. At first the research team tried to contact the selected Public Accountant Office via telephone and obtained answers, some received and obtained sent questionnaires and some did not accept the consideration due to the existence of the Covid - 19 pandemic so that many auditors were running working from home. At the chosen and willing Public Accounting Firm, the research team came directly to the chosen Public Accounting Firm with a letter of research and questionnaire. In addition, the research team also distributed questionnaires through Google Form by asking for help filling out the questionnaire to several senior colleagues, partners and managers who work in selected Public Accounting Firms.

Variable measurements are determined using a Likert scale. Likert scale is a 5-point scale that allows a respondent to answer questions by choosing points that are considered neutral if there are questions that are given doubting the respondent. To prevent the answers that are less convincing or biased, the use of the Likert scale uses 4 points with a score of 4 for the highest points and a score of 1 for the lowest points. The following is a Likert scale used in the questionnaire:

1. score 1: strongly disagree (SD),
2. score 2: disagree (D)
3. score 3: agree (A)
4. score 4: strongly agree (SA)

Data analysis techniques used in this study used the Partial Least Square (PLS) program. Before processing the data, Outer Model is first performed on the data, then collecting data from users of measurements to find out the accuracy and consistency of the data. Furthermore, using the Inner Model, descriptive statistical tests and hypothesis testing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The questionnaire distribution period was carried out from May 8, 2020 to June 10, 2020. Researchers distributed questionnaires to all respondents who work at selected public accounting firms in the city of Jakarta, Indonesia. The total respondents that were sampled in this study were 90 respondents from 18 selected Public Accounting Firms (can be seen in appendix 2).

Table 1

Distribution of Delivery and Returning Questionnaires

No	Information	Total
1	Spread Questionnaire	110
2	Questionnaire Not Returned	10
3	Questionnaire returned	100
4	Data that can be processed	90
5	Data that cannot be processed	10

Source: Processed Data

Based on table 1 above, the research team distributed questionnaires to respondents totaling 110 copies. Questionnaires that did not return as many as 10, then questionnaires returned to researchers as many as 100. Questionnaires that could be processed as many as 90, there were 10 questionnaire differences because the 10 questionnaires did not match what researchers wanted and the answers to the questionnaire were less convincing. So it can be concluded that from 100 questionnaires received by researchers, only 90 can be processed. The description of the data in this study which includes the independent variables namely

the behavior of auditors who are proxied as audit experience, compliance pressure and independence as well as the dependent variable namely audit judgment can be seen in appendix 3 to appendix 6.

Data Quality Test

Data quality test is used in order to find out whether the questionnaire used is valid or valid, if the answer from the measured questionnaire is answered that is able to produce statements in a consistent or reliable form.

1. Measurement models (Outer Model)

a. Convergent Validity Test

Measurement models using convergent validity are calculated using the relationship between item scores or component scores using construct scores measured using PLS. Individual reflection values can be declared large if it can have a correlation of more than 0.70 for the construct to be calculated and if the loading factor value is smaller than 0.70 then the indicator is said to be invalid and removed from the construct, but for the first stage research on scale development with calculation of loading values 0.5 to 0.6 has been deemed to meet the test requirements and is acceptable (Ghozali & Latan, 2015 p. 37). The results of the initial path diagram validity testing using Smart PLS 3.2.8 show the path diagram that has been formed, which is as follows:

Figure 2
Outer 1st model

Source: Smart PLS 3.2.8 output

Based on the outer Loading factor path diagram above, the value of indicators with a value of less than 0.50 will be dropped from the analyst test because it can cause bias in this research model. After being outlier some indicators will be explained in the picture below.

Figure 3.
Outer 2nd model

Source: Smart PLS 3.2.8 output

Based on figure 3. The outer 2nd model shows that all outer loading values are above 0.5 and the smallest outer loading value is 0.674 for the X_{12}^2 indicator so that it can be declared valid or has fulfilled convergent validity. The audit experience variable contains 7 statements and all of these statements fulfill convergent validity. The obedience pressure variable contains 12 statements but only 4 statements can meet convergent validity. Then the Independence variable contains 9 statements but only 4 statements that meet convergent validity. And the Audit Judgment variable of the 7 statements that there is only 1 statement that meets convergent validity.

b. Discriminant Validity Test

The SmartPLS 3.2.8 software output results obtained Fornell-Lacker Criterium value and AVE for each indicator which is as follows:

Table 2.
Fornell-Lacker Criterium

	Audit Judgment (Y)	Independence (X3)	Audit Experience (X1)	Compliance Pressure (X2)
Audit Judgment (Y)	1.000			
Independence (X3)	0.529	0.810		
Audit Experience (X1)	0.46	0.592	0.768	
Compliance Pressure (X2)	0.352	0.634	0.510	0.789

Source: Processed Data

In table 2 above shows the discriminant validity through the Fornell-Lacker Criterium table has a value above 0.60 in each variable. The audit experience variable (X1) has a value of 0.768. The Compliance Pressure variable (X2) has a total value of 0.789. The Independence variable (X3) has a value of 0.810. The Audit Judgment variable has a value of 1,000. That is, that all constructs of audit experience, compliance pressure, independence and Audit Judgment are valid or valid.

Based on discriminant validity above, it can also be seen with other methods, namely the value of the square root of average variance extracted (AVE), the model can be declared good if it has a AVE value, each construct above 0.50 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015 p. 40). The following is the AVE value in this study:

Table 3.
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Rata - Rata Varians Diekstrak (AVE)
Audit Judgment (Y)	1.000
Audit Experience(X1)	0.589
Compliance Pressure (X2)	0.623
Independence (X3)	0.656

Source: Processed Data

Based on table 3 shows the AVE value above 0.50 on all variables found in this research model. The smallest AVE value in this study is 0.589 in the audit experience variable (X1). This means that the audit experience variable, compliance pressure, independence and Audit Judgment are declared valid or valid because the value of each variable is above 0.50.

c. Reliability Test

There are two test criteria to see this reliability test, namely composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha. The construct can be said to be reliable if the composite reliability and cronbach's alpha values are above 0.70 then it can be stated if the construct has good reliability.

The Smart PLS 3.2.8 software output results show the Composite Reability and Cronbach'a Alpha values for each construct as below:

Table 4.
Composite Reliability

	Reliabilitas Composit
Audit Judgment (Y)	1.000

Audit Experience (X1)	0.909
Compliance Pressure (X2)	0.868
Independence (X3)	0.884

Source: Processed Data

Table 4 above shows that for all constructs the value of Composite Reliability is above 0.70, meaning that all constructs in the model meet the criteria. The lowest value of Composite Reliability in this study was 0.884 for the independence variable. Then it can be concluded that all variables have good reliability in each construct. Reliability testing can also be strengthened while looking at Cronbach's Alpha values, with the results below:

Table 5.
Cronbach's Alpha

	cronbach's Alpha
Audit Judgment (Y)	1.000
Audit Experience (X1)	0.884
Compliance Pressure (X2)	0.805
Independence (X3)	0.825

Source: Processed Data

In table 5 shows the lowest value of Cronbach's Alpha in this study as much as 0.805 on the compliance pressure variable (X2). Cronbach's alpha values can be said to be good if all the results of the construct values are above 0.70 (Ghozali & Latan, 2015 p. 155). So it can be concluded that all variables have very good reliability to each construct.

2. Structural Model (Inner Model)

The inner model can be done because it knows the value of R-Squares, Q-Square, F2 Test (Effect Size) and path coefficient.

a. R-Squares

Tests on the structural model are carried out by knowing the value of R-Squares which becomes the goodness-fit test of the model.

Table 6.
R- Squares

	R-Squares
Audit Judgment (Y)	0.313

Source: Processed Data

In table 6 the R-Squares value from Audit Judgment can be obtained which is equal to 0.313, then it shows that the latent independent variables namely audit experience, obedience pressure and independence can explain the dependent latent variable namely Audit Judgment by 31% and a difference of 69% illustrated by other variables outside this study.

b. Q-Squares

Q-squares can be used to assess how good observations are released from the model and can estimate the parameters. The value of q-squares must be greater than 0 (zero), which means that it shows the model has predictive relevance, while if the q-squares value is below 0 (zero) then the model does not have enough predictive relevance (Ghozali & Latan, 2015 p.79).

Q-Square calculation is carried out using the equation:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R_1^2) (1 - R_2^2) \dots (1 - R_n^2)$$

Note:

Q^2 has a range value $0 < Q^2 < 1$ that is, if getting closer to 1 means having a better model.

$$\begin{aligned} Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R_1^2) \\ &= 1 - (1 - 0.313) \\ &= 0.313 \end{aligned}$$

The results show that... Q^2 amounted to 0.313. According to criteria $0 < 0.313 < 1$ getting closer to 1, model is said to be good.

c. Uji F² (Effect Size)

Table 7.
Uji F² (Effect size)

	Audit Judgment (Y)	Independence (X3)	Audit Experience (X1)	Compliance Pressure (X1)
Audit Judgment (Y)				
Audit Experience (X1)	0.048			
Compliance Pressure (X2)	0.000			
Independence (X3)	0.120			

Source: Processed Data

According to Cohen (1988) the effect size test is a measurement to find out whether or not the effect used in certain variables on other variables. The F² value can be concluded that 0.02 is weak, 0.15 moderate, and 0.35 strong (Ghozali & Latan, 2015, p.78).

Based on table 7 above, it can be understood the value of the Independence variable of 0.120 which means it has a moderate influence on the structural level. The audit experience variable has a value of 0.048 which means it has a moderate influence on the structural level. And compliance pressure has a value of 0,000 which means it has a weak influence on the structural level.

d. Path Coefficients

In the processed data for the structural model in Path Coefficient Analysis the results are as follows:

Table 8.
Value of the Path Analysis Coefficient Results

	Audit Judgment (Y)	Independence (X3)	Audit Experience (X1)	Compliance Pressure (X1)
Audit Experience (X1)	0.407			
Compliance Pressure (X2)	-0.023			
Independence (X3)	0.231			

Source: Processed Data

Table 8 shows the results of the path analysis coefficient. The coefficient value of the path analysis of the Audit Experience variable to Audit Judgment is 0.407 and there is a positive relationship. The coefficient value of the path stress analysis of compliance with Audit Judgment is -0.023 and there is a negative correlation. then the coefficient value of the analysis of the Independence variable path to Audit Judgment is 0.231 and there is a positive relationship.

Figure 4.
Inner Model

Source: Smart PLS 3.2.8 Output Results

Hypothesis testing

1. t test - statistics

This t-statistic test is used to determine whether there is a significant influence or not between audit experience (X1), compliance pressure (X2), and independence (X3) to Audit Judgment (Y). Known $t_{table} = 1.98$ which is calculated through a formula = $TINV(0.5, n-k)$ with a confidence level of 5%.

Table 9.

t-Statistics Test Results

			Original Samples (O)	Sample Means (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistic (IO/ STDEV I)	P Values
Independence Judgment (X3)	->	Audit	0.407	0.394	0.124	3.270	0.001
Audit Experience Judgment (X1)	->	Audit	0.231	0.251	0.102	2.257	0.024
Compliance Audit Judgment (X2)	Pressure ->		-0.023	-0.002	0.101	0.233	0.816

Source: Processed Data

Based on table 9 above, it can be seen that the results of the t-test statistic of audit experience variables to Audit Judgment have value t_{count} a number 2.257 while it is of value t_{table} a number 1.98 until it can be concluded $t_{count} > t_{table}$. Then it can be seen from the significant value of the audit experience variable has a significant value of 0.024 which has a meaning smaller than the significant level of 0.050 ($0.024 < 0.050$) so that H_A be accepted and H_0 be rejected.

While the compliance pressure variable to Audit Judgment in table 9 above shows the value t_{count} sebesar 0.233 while it is of value t_{table} a number 1.98 It can be concluded $t_{count} < t_{table}$. Furthermore, it can be known based on the significant value of obedience pressure variable has a significant value of 0.816 which has a meaning greater than a significant level of 0.050 ($0.816 > 0.050$) then H_0 be accepted and H_A be rejected.

For the Independence variable to Audit Judgment in table 9 shows the value t_{count} sejumlah 3.270 while it is of value t_{table} a number 1.98 It can be concluded $t_{count} > t_{table}$. Then the next can be seen from the significant value of the Independence variable has a significant value of 0.001 meaning smaller than the significant level of 0.050 ($0.001 < 0.050$) so that H_A be accepted and H_0 be rejected.

Discussion

1. Effect of Audit Experience on Audit Judgment

The audit experience variable has a significant effect on Audit Judgment. This research is in accordance with the theory used, namely the attribution theory that explains a person's perceptions of events around them, by understanding their arguments for the events they experienced. Then this audit experience sees from the perspective of the culprit, highly experienced auditors will maintain their behavior when or at work.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Murtadha & Imam (2018), Ardiani, (2019), Nyoman & Tibe, (2019), Ariyantini, (2014), where their research shows that "audit experience has a significant influence on Audit Judgment. ". This research is also in line with research conducted by Sofiani & Tjondro (2019) who said that high audit experience will improve skills so that the ability to think and act will be better too.

The results of this study can be seen from the questionnaire analysis that produces an average value of 3.35 rounded up to 3 which means that the audit experience variable has a scale of agreed answers, which means that the audit experience it has received so far can have an influence on Audit Judgment. Conclusions can be drawn about the auditor that if the auditor who already has high audit experience will understand in making a decision because of learning from previous experiences in order to produce higher quality audit results.

2. Effects of Compliance Pressure on Audit Judgments

Compliance pressure does not have a significant effect on Audit Judgment. It can be seen that compliance pressure can increase if the respondent in this study is an auditor who works at a Public Accounting Firm (KAP) in DKI Jakarta does not fulfill the client's desire to deviate from professional standards if he does not want to have a problem with the client (auditee), that an auditor will obey the auditee's wishes even though

they will conflict with the professional standards set by IAPI (Indonesian Public Accountants Association). Not only is the pressure from the auditee alone, there are also pressures from the supervisor of the auditor himself who exert pressure such as work that must be completed immediately, because of the limited time for reporting the audit was issued. This makes the problem within the auditor itself related to the pressure received during the assignment period.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Maria & Nadya (2019), Priyoga & Ayem (2019), Drupadi & Sudana (2015), Sofiani & Tjondro (2019), TH Komalasari et al., (2019) who said if the variables compliance pressure has no effect on Audit Judgment. Due to the amount of pressure faced by the auditor when the audit assignment takes place, it does not affect the judgment (decision). The higher the pressure faced by an auditor, then this will not affect the accuracy of the judgment made because an auditor will try to fulfill his professional responsibilities even though on the other hand are required to obey orders from the entity being examined and his supervisor.

3. Effect of Independence on Audit Judgment

Independence has a significant influence on Audit Judgment. Independence means not being easily influenced. An auditor is not justified to carry out acts that can be in favor of anyone's interests. A good auditor will always uphold his independence. Likewise, in each assignment, an auditor will be able to maintain the attitude of independence as an auditor.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Nadya & Maria (2019), Ramdani & Hendy (2019), Komalasari & Hernawati, (2015) suggesting that "Independence has a significant influence on Audit Judgment". The greater the independence that the auditor has, resulting in the more thorough audit judgment that will be issued. When the Judgment composer, an auditor cannot side with any need, even if it is the client or the party who has the need for an audit report, Independence is the basis for the superiority of the auditor's report (Drupadi & Sudana, 2015).

This study is in accordance with the theory used in this study, namely the attribution theory. According to the Attribution attribution theory, it means that behavior is free from other influences, therefore an auditor cannot be controlled and is not bound to any party in making decisions. The higher the level of independence of an auditor, the more accurate the resulting judgments.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to find empirical evidence and to analyze the significant influence of auditor behavior that is proxied by audit experience variables, compliance pressure, and independence of Audit Judgment. Based on the results of research and discussions that have been completed using the Partial Least Square program, conclusions can be drawn:

1. The audit experience variable significantly influences the Audit Judgment.
2. The compliance pressure variable does not significantly influence Audit Judgment.
3. Independence variable significantly influences Audit Judgment.

The limitation in this research is especially in the activities of distributing questionnaires because of the Covid - 19 pandemic so that many public accountant firms are unable to accept this research questionnaire on the grounds that many of their auditors are working from home. Therefore, the distribution of questionnaires cannot be done maximally, because one public accountant firm is only able to accept 5 to 7 questionnaires, so the research team must look for another public accountant firm that is willing to accept the questionnaire.

In addition, this study also does not include other auditor behavior variables that affect audit judgment, for example: time budget pressure, auditor knowledge, auditor competence, audit expertise, gender, and others. This study also did not test on each questionnaire called the Plot Test.

Suggestions for future researchers to be able to multiply other variables that are indicated will affect Audit Judgments such as gender, auditor competence, and others. This study only focuses on the behavior of auditors in the Jakarta City area, so the next researcher is advised to expand the scope of the study area to obtain maximum results. As for the auditors, in carrying out their duties, they always obey the rules and work in a professional manner and uphold honesty or independence in order to produce better Audit Judgments. And for public accountant firms to always ensure that auditors assigned have an independent attitude, obey all rules and not receive pressure from any party.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- i. a, H., a, M., & Kusumawati, A. (2018). *the Effect of Self - Efficacy and Obedience Pressure on Audit Judgment By Using Task Complexity and Moral Reasoning As the Moderating Variable. International Journal of Advanced Research, Volume 6, No.10, hlm. 238–248.*
- ii. Abbas, D., & Basuki, B. (2019). *Pengaruh Profesionalisme auditor dan pengalaman auditor terhadap Audit Judgment (KAP Provinsi Banten). Simposium Nasional Multidisiplin (SinaMu), hlm. 1–12.*
- iii. Agustini, N., & Merkusiwati, N. (2016). *Pengaruh Tekanan Kepatuhan, Senioritas Auditor Dan Tekanan Anggaran Waktu Terhadap Audit Judgment. E-Jurnal Akuntansi, Volume 15, No. 1, hlm. 433–462.*
- iv. Ardiani, A. & D. (2019). *Kompetensi Profesional terhadap Audit Judgment. Ardiani Ika Sulistyawati , Aprih Santoso , Dina Sita Prastiti Corresponding author : Ardiani Ika Sulistyawati. Volume 6, No.1, hlm. 61–72.*
- v. Ariyantini, sujana & nyoman. (2014). *Pengaruh Pengalaman Auditor, Tekanan Kepatuhan Dan Kompleksitas Tugas Terhadap Audit Judgement. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Cendekiawan, Volume 2, No.1, hlm. 2*
- vi. Cnn Indonesia (2018). *Kronologi SNP Finance dari 'Tukang Kredit' ke 'Tukang Bobol'. Retrieved March 15,2019, from https://m.cnnindonesia.com/ekonomi/20180926143029-78-333372/kronologi-snp-finance-dari-tukang-kredit-ke-tukang-bobol*
- vii. Drupadi, M., & Sudana, I. (2015). *Pengaruh Keahlian Auditor, Tekanan Kepatuhan Dan Independensi Pada Audit Judgment. E-Jurnal Akuntansi, Volume 12, No.3, hlm. 623–655.*
- viii. Farma, H. dan christian. (2016). *Analisis Faktor–Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Audit Judgment. Jurnal EMBA, Volume 5, No.1, hlm. 20–29.*
- ix. Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Squares: Konsep, Teknik, dan Aplikasi Menggunakan Program SmartPLS 3.0 edisi ke-2. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.*
- x. Hendy, R. &. (2019). *Pengaruh gender, tekanan kepatuhan, independensi, tekanan anggaran waktu dan pengalaman terhadap audit judgment. Volume 4, No.2, hlm. 23–34.*
- xi. IAPI. (2013). *Standar Audit (SA) 315 Pengidentifikasian dan Penilaian Risiko Kesalahan Penyajian Material melalui Pemahaman atas Entitas dan Lingkungannya.*
- xii. Irwan, & Adam, K. (2015). *Metode Partial Least Square (PLS) Dan Terapannya. Jurnal Teknosains, Volume 9, No.1, hlm. 53–68.*
- xiii. Komalasari, R., & Hernawati, E. (2015). *Pengaruh Independensi, Kompleksitas Tugas, Dan Gender Terhadap Audit Judgment. Jurnal Neo-Bis, Volume 9, No.2, hlm. 66–86.*
- xiv. Komalasari, T. H., Syofyan, E., & Mulyani, E. (2019). *Pengaruh Gender, Tekanan Kepatuhan, Kompleksitas Tugas, Pengalaman Auditor, Pengetahuan Auditor, dan Kompleksitas Dokumen Audit Terhadap Audit Judgment (Studi Empiris Pada Badan Pemeriksa Keuangan Republik Indonesia Perwakilan Provinsi Sumatera Barat). Jurnal Ekplorasi Akuntansi, Volume 1, No.1, hlm. 459–469.*
- xv. Maria, N. &. (2019). *Pengaruh pengalaman auditor, keahlian auditor, independensi, tekanan kepatuhan dan kompleksitas tugas terhadap audit judgment. Ultima Accounting. Volume 11, No.1, hlm. 58–80.*
- xvi. Murtadha, I. A. (2018). *Pengaruh Gender, Anggaran Waktu dan Pengalaman Auditor terhadap Audit Judgment (Studi Empiris Pada Kantor Akuntan Publik (KAP) dan Badan Pemeriksa Keuangan (BPK) di Sumatra Barat). Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Volume 1, hlm. 1–19.*
- xvii. Nugraha, A. P., & Januarti, H. I. (2015). *Pengaruh Gender , Pengalaman , Keahlian Auditor Dan Tekanan Kepatuhan Terhadap Auditor Judgement Moderasi Pada Bpk Ri Jawa Tengah. Diponegoro Journal of Accounting, Volume 4, No. 4, hlm. 1–11.*
- xviii. Nyoman, T. &. (2019). *Pengaruh kompleksitas tugas, pengalaman auditor, skeptisme dan tekanan anggaran waktu terhadap audit judgment. Journal Research Accounting. Volume 1, No.1, hlm. 30–44.*
- xix. Pangesti, D. B., Setyowati, W., Ekonomika, F., Stikubank, U., Masalah, L. B., & Keputusan, T. P. (2018). *Pengaruh Persepsi Etis, Pengalaman Auditor, Tekanan Kepatuhan dan Kompleksitas Tugas Terhadap Kualitas Audit Judgement. Jurnal Prosiding SENDI, hlm. 978–979.*

- xx. *Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2015 “Praktik Akuntan Publik”*
- xxi. *Peraturan Menteri Keuangan Republik Indonesia Nomor 154, PMK 01 Tahun 2017 “Pembinaan dan Pengawasan Akuntan Publik”*
- xxii. *Peraturan Otoritas Jasa Keuangan Nomor 13 /POJK.03/2017 “Penggunaan Jasa Akuntan Publik serta Kantor Akuntan Publik pada Kegiatan Jasa Keuangan”.*
- xxiii. *Priyoga, I., & Ayem, S. (2019). Pengaruh Tekanan Kepatuhan, Gender, Kompleksitas Tugas, Independensi, Dan Pengalaman Auditor Terhadap Audit Judgment (Studi Kasus Pada Badan Pengawasan Keuangan Dan Pembangunan Perwakilan Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta). Jurnal Kajian Bisnis, Volume 27, No.1, hlm. 61–72.*
- xxiv. *Putra & rani. (2016). Pengaruh Gender, Kompleksitas Tugas, Pengalaman Auditor, Dan Kompetensi Profesional Terhadap Audit Judgment. JMBI UNSRAT (Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Bisnis Dan Inovasi Universitas Sam Ratulangi)., Volume 6, No. 1.*
- xxv. *Rahmatika, N. N., Putra, D., Mahardika, K., & Telkom, U. (2019). Pengaruh pengetahuan, tekanan kepatuhan dan independensi terhadap audit judgment (studi kasus pada kantor akuntan publik (KAP) di Kota Bandung. Jurnal Ekonomi dan Bisnis, Volume 6, No.1, hlm. 694–704.*
- xxvi. *Sofiani, M. M. O. L., & Tjondro, E. (2019). Pengaruh Tekanan Kepatuhan, Pengalaman Audit, dan Audit Tenure terhadap Audit Judgment. Tax & Accounting Review, Volume 4, No.1, hlm. 1–10.*
- xxvii. *Sumanto, A., & Rosdiana, M. (2019). Pengaruh Pengalaman Auditor, Tekanan Kepatuhan Dan Kompleksitas Tugas Terhadap Audit Judgment. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Cendekiawan, Volume 2.*
- xxviii. *Tampubolon, L. (2018). Dampak Tekanan Kepatuhan, Pengetahuan, Dan Pengalaman Auditor Terhadap Audit Judgment. Jurnal Keuangan dan Perbankan, Volume 14, No.2, hlm. 62-70.*
- xxix. *Uma sekaran dan Roger Bougie. (2017). Metode Penelitian untuk Bisnis (pendekatan pengembangan keahlian). Edisi 6 Buku 1. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat*

Appendix 1. Respondent Demographics

Characteristics	Description	Frequency	Percentage
Age of Respondents	<25 year	30	33%
	25 - 35 year	47	52%
	36 - 50 year	8	9%
	> 50 year	5	6%
Position	Senior	82	92%
	Partner	4	4%
	Manager	4	4%
Education	Associate	5	6%
	Bachelor	79	87%
	Master	5	6%
	Doctor	1	1%
Work experience	2 year	42	47%
	3 - 6 year	30	33%
	7 - 10 year	10	11%
	> 10 year	8	9%
Average Number of Audit Assignments for 1 Year	1 - 5 Assignments	47	52%
	6 - 10 Assignments	25	28%
	11 - 15 Assignments	8	9%
	> 15 Assignments	10	11%

Source: processed data

Appendix 2. List of selected public accountant firms in the study

Respondent Number	Name of Public Accountant Firm
1 to 6	Anderson, Amril & Rekan
7 to 11	Armen, Budiman & Rekan
12 to 16	Drs. Bambang Sudaryono & Rekan
17 to 21	Drs. Chaeroni & Rekan
22 to 28	Djoko, Sidik & Indra
29 to 33	Doli, Bambang, Sulistiyanto, Dadang & Ali
34 to 38	Ishak, Saleh, Soewondo & Rekan
39 to 44	Iwan Siswandi M.Ak
45 to 49	Jamaludin, Ardi, Sukimto & Rekan
50 to 56	Kumalahadi, Kuncara, Sugeng Pamudjio & Rekan
57 to 61	Purba Lauddin & Rekan
62 to 66	Ratna Widjaja
67 to 72	Sahat MT & Rekan
73 to 77	Tendy Wato & Ifen Tjhai
78 to 82	Tjhin Tjiap Lung & Rekan
83 to 87	Yuwono H
88 to 89	PKF Hadiwinata
90	Sigit Sunarno, CPA

Source: IAPI 2019 Directory

Appendix 3. Frequency and Average Distribution Regarding Judgment Audit

No	Statements	Score				Total	Mean
		SD	D	A	SA		
		1	2	3	4		
1	Considerations related to materiality require the skills and expertise that the auditor has	0	3	64	23	290	3,22
2	If the auditor gives a weak explanation of the results of the audit report, the auditor will find audit risk	0	4	72	14	280	3,11
3	The auditor's competence influences his judgment to determine relevant audit evidence in accordance with the capabilities of the auditor.	1	1	71	17	284	3,15
4	An understanding of the client's internal control system affects the effectiveness and efficiency of audits.	0	0	52	38	308	3,42
5	The determination of audit procedures is influenced by the time the audit report is completed and the audit risk	0	3	68	19	286	3,18
6	Poor audit structure does not impede audit procedures	16	33	30	11	216	2,4
7	Auditors who are under the wrong instructions from superiors will increase audit risk	0	6	58	26	290	3,22
Total		17	50	415	148	1954	21,7
Mean							3,11

Source: processed data

Appendix 4. Frequency and Average Distribution of Audit Experiences

No	Statements	Score				Total	Mean
		SD	D	A	SA		
		1	2	3	4		
1	The longer I become an auditor, the more I understand how to deal with entities / objects of examination to obtain the necessary data and information	0	0	47	43	313	3,48
2	The more I worked as an auditor, the more I was able to find out relevant information in order to take consideration to make a decision	0	1	51	38	307	3,41
3	The longer I worked as an auditor, the more I could detect errors made by the examination object	0	2	62	26	294	3,27

4	The longer I became an auditor, the easier it was for me to find the cause of error and to be able to provide recommendations to eliminate or minimize that cause	0	5	55	30	295	3,28
5	The many tasks faced give me an opportunity to learn from the failures and successes that have been experienced	0	3	48	39	306	3,4
6	The number of tasks received can trigger me to complete the task quickly.	0	8	54	28	290	3,22
7	The more companies I audit, the better the audits I conduct in the future.	0	3	47	40	307	3,41
Total		0	22	364	244	2112	23,47
Mean							3,35

Source: processed data

Appendix 5. Frequency and Average Distribution Regarding Compliance Pressure

No	Statements	Score				Total	Mean
		SD	D	A	SA		
		1	2	3	4		
1	I will obey the client's wishes even though they are contrary to the auditor's professional standards	42	29	14	5	162	1,8
2	I do not want to get into trouble with a client if I violate an order given by the client	16	38	32	4	204	2,27
3	I will not oppose the client's desire to deviate.	30	31	23	6	185	2,06
4	I am worried that my client will move to another auditor's office, if I cannot report the audit results within the specified time.	11	39	35	5	214	2,38
5	If I misrepresent fairness on financial statements, then I violate the skepticism of professionalism	7	7	60	16	265	2,94
6	I do not want to get into trouble with my boss if he does not obey his desire to deviate from professional standards.	24	39	18	9	192	2,13
7	I will be expelled from work if I do not obey my supervisor's orders to do things that are contrary to professional standards	24	38	23	5	189	2,1
8	I will obey superiors' orders even though I will have a moral burden because they are against professional standards.	20	44	21	5	191	2,12
9	I will defy the orders of my superiors and choose to quit my job if I am forced to do things that are contrary to professional standards	2	4	60	24	286	3,18
10	In the trust given by the public to me as an accountant, I should show my dedication to the public by achieving skepticism about professionalism	0	3	60	27	294	3,27
11	Auditor's considerations need to be followed for the preparation of significant audit decisions based on a code of professionalism.	0	3	60	27	294	3,27
12	I will oppose orders from superiors if I do not issue an opinion on fairness matters in the financial statements	3	14	47	26	276	3,07
Total		179	289	453	159	2752	30,59
Mean							2,54

Source: processed data

Appendix 6. Frequency and Average Distribution of Independence

No	Statements	Score				Total	Mean
		SD	D	A	SA		
		1	2	3	4		
1	The preparation of the audit program is free from interference by the leadership or other parties in determining, eliminating or modifying certain parts that are examined	1	20	61	8	256	2,84
2	The preparation of the audit program is free from the efforts of other parties in determining the subject of inspection work from the manager	0	15	63	12	267	2,97
3	In conducting the examination, I agree that there is cooperation with other parties that do not enforce the independence requirements according to the standards of public accountants, so I cannot be called an expert..	9	18	54	9	243	2,7
4	Supervision report from the auditor's effort to influence the examiner's consideration to the contents of the examiner's report	0	8	70	12	274	3,04
5	The auditor's experience and skills affect the audit fees he receives based on the quality of the audit results	2	3	69	16	279	3,1
6	Audits are conducted on clients who do not have an interest relationship related to the family environment or close friends with the auditor	1	2	50	37	303	3,37
7	Auditors are always honest in their words and deeds and always obey based on the code of ethics of public accountants	0	1	45	44	313	3,48
8	The auditor states that freedom of thought and opinion with shareholders must be in accordance with agreed policies and laws.	0	0	65	25	295	3,28
9	The auditor in expressing his opinion must be in accordance with applicable law in making the audit report	0	0	57	33	303	3,37
Total		13	67	534	196	2.533	28,14
Mean							3,12

Source: processed data